

Southern California CSU DNP Consortium

California State University, Fullerton
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MAMMOGRAPHY DATABASE: ADHERENCE TRACKING FOR WOMAN
VETERANS

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

For the degree of

DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

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ABSTRACT

The Veterans Healthcare Administration (VHA) recognizes women Veterans (WVs) as the fastest growing demographic group within the Veteran population. To reduce mortality and deaths from breast cancer, VHA guidelines recommend routine mammography screenings for women ages 50 to 74. As of Fall 2014, this Southern California large federal healthcare system (HCS) organization did not have a systematic way to monitor outpatient WV recommended screening due dates or follow-ups within the complex electronic healthcare records (EHR). Given this, a population-based Microsoft Access database was developed as a tool to proactively manage preventive mammography screenings by serving as a reliable tracking and reminder system. When used as a tracking tool by system-wide clinics, it will help improve screening adherence, and should decrease or eliminate the potential that WVs would miss follow-up appointments for abnormal findings. Following implementation, evaluation of database effectiveness will include comparison of 3-month baseline preventive performance measures and abnormal follow-up exams (manual tracking) to a 3-month period after implementation of the database system. User satisfaction will be assessed using the Questionnaire for User Interaction Satisfaction (QUIS). Once in use, consideration may be given to expanding the database to track other key prevention measures (e.g., pap smears) with appropriate follow-up metrics.

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BACKGROUND

Problem Statement

Within the Veteran Healthcare Administration (VHA), women Veterans (WVs) are the minority gender (U.S. Department of Veterans Affairs, National Center for Veterans Analysis and Statistics [USDVA, NCVAS], 2013). The VHA recognizes them as the fastest growing demographic group within the Veteran population. As of September 2013, WVs numbered 2,271,222 in the United States. California is one of the top five states in terms of numbers with 184,774 WVs (USDVA, NCVAS, 2013). In Southern California, a large federal HCS organization serves approximately 3,184 WVs.

To reduce mortality and deaths from breast cancer, VHA guidelines recommend routine mammography screenings for women ages 50 to 74 (U.S. Department of Veterans Affairs, VHA National Center for Health Promotion and Disease Prevention [USDVA, NCP], 2012). Nationally, breast cancer ranks as one of the three most common cancers and cancer-related deaths among women (U.S. Department of Health and Human Services, Center for Disease Control and Prevention and National Cancer Institute [USDHHS, CDCP & NCI], 2013); early detection has been shown to decrease breast cancer mortality. The American Cancer Society (ACS) estimates for breast cancer in the United States in 2015 are about 231,840 new cases of invasive breast cancer will be diagnosed and about 40,290 women will die from breast cancer (American Cancer Society [ACS], 2015). Recognizing the high prevalence of breast cancer and the effectiveness of early detection, the NCP, VHA Directive, and VHA Handbook provide clinical screening guidelines for breast cancer (USDVA, NCP).

In fiscal year 2013, the HCS organization fell below the VHA national standards in meeting their breast cancer screening performance measure for women ages 50 to 69. The performance measures are reported by the External Peer Review Program (EPRP), an external program that is under contract to collect data from electronic medical records at the VHA. Staff members from EPRP provides the organization with a database of information that, for each indicator (e.g., breast cancer screening), reflects randomly sampled persons from the total HCS organization population. Reports from this database are used in plans for meeting performance measures through comparison, evaluation, and benchmarking of clinical care with external organizations.

The HCS organization's 4th quarter 2013 year-to-date breast screening prevention measure was 71%, compared to the VHA national performance measure at 85% (Table 1). This placed the organizations data two standard deviations below the mean (statistically different). In October 2013 and the new fiscal year 2014, the performance measure was changed to include women ages 50 to 74. The change was in response to U. S. Preventive Services Task Force (USPSTF) and the NCP guidance on clinical preventive services (USDVA, NCP, 2012; U. S. Preventive Services Task Force [USPSTF], 2013).

Table 1

FY2013 Breast Screening Performance Measures.

Measure Name	Facility	Quarter 1	Quarter 2	Quarter 3	Quarter 4	FY2013 Cum %
CA – Women age 50-69 screened for Breast Cancer	Large Federal Healthcare System	62%	81%	73%	53%	71%
	National	86%	86%	84%	84%	85%

While the federal HCS organization offers services for active duty service members, dependents of services members, and Veterans, this project will focus only on women discharged from active duty or released under conditions other than dishonorable discharge (Moulta-Ali, 2014). According to the NCP, it is important to focus on this group of WVs to ensure that organization is meeting one of the VHA's Mission Critical Measures. The critical measure requirement is achieving breast cancer screenings for women ages 50 through 74 years to complete mammograms every 1-2 years (USDVA, NCP, 2012).

In order to meet the national performance measures standards, it is important to assure that women are compliant with mammograms at the recommended time intervals.

Local Context for this Project

Collaboration began with the Women's Health Clinic (WHC) in response to the need to assess the mammography program and improve the performance measures. The initial aim of this doctoral project was to contribute to the performance improvement of the mammography program by providing an analysis of WV demographics and contributing factors that posed potential barriers to prevention screening adherence, which would have informed recommendations for practice change. Unfortunately, the project took a turn midway through the doctoral program, when I was faced with the obstacle of attaining institutional review board approval from the federal HCS.

After returning to the list of challenges reviewed with the WHC staff, the new focus of the doctoral project became creation of an integrated tracking and follow-up technology into their current mammography program. The WHC uses the Computerized Patient Record System (CPRS) mammography clinical reminder system and a weekly list

provided of WVs scheduled for an upcoming appointment, not related to mammography, as tools for prompting communication with WVs. The advantage of this electronic health record (EHR) is that when WVs have face-to-face visits or any other communications where the CPRS is accessed, the clinical reminder will display if a mammogram is due, thus providing an opportunity to communicate the need for a mammography. The disadvantage is that if the WHC does not have contact with the WV, there is no way to know whether there is a need for screening or follow-up. As it exists, this system thus disregards WVs who infrequently visit the WHC, and can delay potential detection and treatment of breast cancer. To provide reassurance to WHC staff as well as improving communication and quality of care for WVs, a method for tracking and follow-up would be of value to decrease missed opportunities for screening, education, and follow-up.

Recommendation for Practice Change

Taking a more proactive role in the health of WVs can provide opportunities to reach out to the at-risk (overdue) and follow up with balanced education of the risks and benefits of having mammograms. Having such an outreach provides an opportunity for WHC staff to have conversations with WVs during calls to inform them of their overdue mammography.

In an integrative review, Edgar and colleagues (2013) made the following evidence-based recommendations:

- Increase women's knowledge of breast cancer risk factors,
- Provide flexible appointment days and times to accommodate work and family,

- Reassurance by health professionals about the mammography experience to women who disclose feelings of anxiety with preventive screening and breast cancer by educating about the benefits of early detection and dismissing stoic views of the disease,
- Assess the socioeconomic and cultural differences,
- Support balanced view of benefits and risks (e.g. false positive, false negative, overtreatment and over diagnosis), and
- Reach out and engage women in informed decision making with comprehensive information, assessment and follow-up.

In an interview, the WHC nurse care manager described the current process and available alerts as appropriate for point-of-care contact. However, she felt that there was room for improvement to proactively manage this population with a user-friendly system to track upcoming due dates and necessary follow-ups. Analysis of the current system identified individual staff calendars being used for tracking and monitoring follow-ups, challenges with timely communication between deliveries of care, including judicious follow-ups due to ineffective practices. This helped determine the need for this DNP project. The WHC could benefit from a monitoring and tracking system (Atlas et al., 2010; Corkery, 2007). Such systems are often referenced as registries or population-based databases.

There are multiple benefits in databases of this type. These include the following:

- Empowering staff to be able to work at the maximum level of licensure with minimal involvement of providers,

- Using the WHC staff (RN Care Manager, Licensed Vocational Nurse (LVN), or clerk) to identify patients due for screening through a report from the database and subsequently, sending a “It’s Time for Your Mammography” letter and a second follow-up letter if no response or completion of mammogram,
- Using the WHC staff to identify WVs who need follow-up and sending an important reminder letter to call to make an appointment.

Women’s preventive health care is provided in a number of clinics at the federal HCS including its community-based outpatient clinics (CBOCs) and by various providers (e.g., medical doctors, nurse practitioners). The implementation of the population-based database tool will capture and provide meaningful information about WVs, which can be analyzed to identify specific contributing factors that affect quality outcomes as well as areas for improvement. Furthermore, it provides a systematic shared approach for communication and evaluation of the mammography program, which should benefit multiple clinics.

Supporting Framework

Healthcare organizations use performance improvement models to improve their performance targeted at improving specific healthcare problems. The literature offers a variety of frameworks, each with individual benefits and sharing a theoretical base to improve performance. Performance improvement projects can work best when all team members agree to a single model to drive their improvements and clarify the outcomes (Dianis & Cummings, 1998). The conceptual framework chosen for this performance improvement project will be the FOCUS – PDCA model (Figure 1).

The PDCA model adopted by the federal HCS provides the framework for the pursuit of excellence in the provision of healthcare through a planned, collaborative, interdisciplinary, organization-wide approach to performance and quality improvement. The Plan, Do, Check and Act Model was originally developed by Shewhart in the 1920s and often referred to as the Shewhart cycle. In the early 1950s, Deming modified the PDCA model and improved its popularity in performance improvement projects. The FOCUS part of the PDCA model was developed by the Hospital Corporation of America (Appendix A) to focus on processes as opposed to individuals (Moen & Norman, 2006).

The intent of the FOCUS-PDCA methodology is to develop processes that directly improve outcomes and advance organizational performance (Taylor et al., 2013). The “**F**” in FOCUS is the vital first step to improvement and that would include **f**inding a process to improve. For the fiscal year 2013, breast cancer clinical screening performance measures for woman 50 to 69 years of age were inconsistent and fell below the national benchmark. This concern was acknowledged as a top priority by leaders and became the focus for this performance improvement project.

The next step is **o**rganizing a team that understands the process that is “**O**” in FOCUS. The ownership of the performance measures lies with the Women’s Health Coordinator. To facilitate this, I put together a small team that comprises a Women’s Designated Provider (WDP), two Registered Nurses (RN) Care Managers, the primary care clinic supervisor, primary care management analyst and the Women’s Health Coordinator. All team members have some degree of direct control over care processes and are the experts in this area of performance improvement.

Clarifying the current knowledge of the process is the “C” in FOCUS. It is important to identify the course of the problem early on to ensure the team is engaged and understands the focus of the improvement process. Often teams jump precipitously into making suggestions for process improvements without a clear understanding about current operations. This can lead to unreliable solutions and make it difficult to reach complete process analysis. Clarifying the current process requires documenting and mapping of the current process. It also requires identifying stakeholders who may be affected by current practices and understanding organizational commitment.

Following the performance improvement model, the “U” in FOCUS is about understanding causes of process variations. In this step, team members question and attempt to identify why the current process is not working. Current benchmark data is acquired to understand the influence of current processes and provide an opportunity to define variations in the process and indicators of success. The benchmark data will later be used to compare measures after recommendations are put into practice.

The final step of FOCUS is “S” when the team will select the performance improvements that will be completed in the process. The team will ensure sufficient data and evidence-based literature exists to support any potential solutions that are recommended. There are several opportunities within the process to improve performance; it is important to consider the improvement opportunity that will most likely succeed and produce the maximum outcome. The process improvement selected will provide a reminder tool for RN Care Managers and Providers to contact WVs about completing a screening mammography at regular intervals, result follow-ups and provide applicable evidence-based recommendations to improve adherence rates.

After the team has clarified current knowledge of the process and process variations, collected and analyzed benchmark data, and completed all FOCUS steps, they will move into the PDCA cycle. The initial step of the PDCA cycle is **p**lanning the improvement and how the improvement will be accomplished. Identification of a measurable outcome is required to determine the degree at which the goal will be accomplished. Proceeding is the “**D**o” phase where the pilot test will be implemented based on identified needs. Observation and data collection occurs during this phase to ensure the improvement is implemented according to the plan and to determine whether a revision in the plan is needed. Following the “Do” phase is the “**C**heck” phase. During the “Check” phase, the team will compare current data to predicted outcomes, and previous benchmark measures collected prior to implementation of the new process. Continuing the cycle is the “**A**ct” phase where the results of the planned changes are accepted and a full scale implementation will occur. If the team did not achieve expected or anticipated outcome results, the “Act” phase is skipped. The team will return to the “Plan” phase to develop some new ideas and move through the cycle again. The process change will need to be documented through policies, procedures, or guidelines. Finally, changes should be communicated throughout the organization and the monitors should continue to assess the effectiveness and sustainability of the change over time.

Figure 1. Focus-PDSA model, adapted for DNP project.

Project Purpose and Goals

The purpose of this quality improvement doctoral project was to address the lack of a systematic user-friendly documenting tool for tracking mammography screenings and follow-ups. Integrating evidence-based interventions into the building of the mammography database, then coupling this information with face-to-face visits with WHC staff or a telephone reminder call can be used to promote screening and follow-ups. Prior to this project, there was no significant HCS effort to take on an electronic method; the practice relies solely on a daily list provided by the management analyst of upcoming WV appointments.

The goals of the project were to include:

1. Identifying both effective and ineffective strategies and processes used by the WHC that promote mammography screenings and track follow-ups.
2. Developing a user friendly population-based Access database tool to promote awareness of upcoming screening reminders, including missed or overdue screening dates and follow-ups. This was done in collaboration with the primary care management analyst, and will be piloted for women 40-74 years of age.

LITERATURE REVIEW

A review of the literature regarding mammography use among WVs and contributing factors that affect adherence was completed using PubMed, Cochrane Library, and Cumulative Index to Nursing & Allied Health Literature (CINAHL) databases with publication dates from 1998–2014. The range in years allowed for inclusion of one of the first comprehensive descriptive studies looking at predictors of WV mammography use (Hynes, Bastian, Rimer, Sloane, & Feussner, 1998). In addition, this review included studies that explored changes in trends over last 16 years. English only published studies were chosen since the focus of project is in a VHA facility. The search terms in PubMed using a Boolean search mode were "Mammography"[Mesh] AND (("women"[MeSH Terms] OR "women"[All Fields]) AND ("Veterans"[MeSH Terms] OR "Veterans"[All Fields])) which resulted in 21 peer-reviewed published articles. Further searches included a combination of PubMed, CINAHL, and Cochrane Library search using the search terms “mammo*,” “breast screening,” “strateg*,” “factors,” “barriers,” “health behavior,” “health promotion,” “access,” and “cost.” One additional separate search returned a surprising zero results which included the terms “military sexual trauma” and “mammography,” “military sexual trauma” and “breast cancer screening,” “military sexual trauma” and “women vet*” and “breast,” and finally “MST” and “women vet*” and “breast.”

Peer-reviewed evidence types included integrative/systematic reviews, qualitative/quantitative studies, and framework literature. This provided a comprehensive literature search that supports utilizing the FOCUS-PDCA model. Furthermore, the qualitative studies can provide background personal beliefs about factors related to breast

cancer screenings that can be utilized to support recommendations and findings from applicable scholarly references that support evidence-based practice educational materials, telephone response scripts, and program process improvements.

Evidence Synthesis

Among the studies selected, eight of the 14 were published using WVs as the focus population. An integrated review of 12 research papers (samples from US, UK, Australia, Canada, and Arab countries) was included that addressed factors that can influence women's decisions to get breast cancer screenings (Edgar, Glackin, Hughes, & Rogers, 2013). A systematic review paper of 26 studies between 1986 and 2004 evaluated the interventions and their effectiveness to increase breast cancer screenings (Baron et al., 2010). One qualitative study sampled 51 WVs to explore their views and decision-making about utilizing VA healthcare (Washington, Kleimann, Michelini, Kleimann, & Canning, 2007). Finally, quantitative studies included were a pragmatic randomized blinded trial (Fortuna et al., 2013), a prospective randomized control trial study (Hegenscheid et al., 2011), and seven cross-sectional, descriptive studies (Dalessandri, Cooper, & Rucker, 1998; Hynes et al., 1998; Lairson, Chan, & Newmark, 2005; Mengeling, Sadler, Torner, & Booth, 2011; Vogt et al., 2006; Washington, Bean-Mayberry, Riopelle, & Yano, 2011; Washington, Yano, Simon, & Sun, 2006). There was a wide range of sample sizes within these 14 studies—from 51 participants in the qualitative study to a larger national electronic database set of 5,477 (Baron et al., 2010; Dalessandri et al., 1998; Edgar et al., 2013; Fortuna et al., 2013; Hegenscheid et al., 2011; Hynes et al., 1998; Lairson et al., 2005; Mengeling et al., 2011; Sabatino et al., 2012; Vogt et al., 2006; Washington et al., 2006, 2007, 2011). Three

studies addressed screening interventions and recommendations for more than one area of interest (breast, cervical and colorectal cancer) in non-Veterans (Baron et al., 2010; Community Preventive Services Task Force [CPSTF], 2012; Sabatino et al., 2012). Three studies evaluated whether a proactive approach to outreach (i.e., informational brochure, letter, phone call, scripted telephone counseling, etc.) would increase the use of mammography in both WVs and the community (Dalessandri et al., 1998; Fortuna et al., 2013; Hegenscheid et al., 2011). The integrative review assessed influencing factors (socio-demographic) that affect participation in breast cancer screening among WVs (Edgar et al., 2013). Two studies evaluated interventions, socio-demographics, and use of VA vs. non-VA facility as potential predictors to mammography use (Hynes et al., 1998; Washington, 2006). Four studies addressed the comprehensive needs, preferences, barriers, and characteristics of VA women (Lairson et al., 2005; Mengeling et al., 2011; Vogt et al., 2006; Washington et al., 2011).

Women Veteran Characteristics

WVs are one of the fastest growing groups of Veterans in VA healthcare (Lairson et al., 2005; Mengeling et al., 2011; Vogt et al., 2006; Washington et al., 2006, 2007, 2011), and are often less healthy than male Veterans or non-Veteran women cohorts (Vogt et al., 2006). Underutilization of the VA systems of care has been recognized as a potential barrier to better health (Vogt et al., 2006; Washington et al., 2007). All studies document that in some way WVs' socio-demographics, access, lack of knowledge of women services, barriers to care, and environment perceptions impact usage of VA clinics/settings for preventive and medical needs.

Characteristics of Women VA Users

Recent studies have found sole VA users to be middle age, primarily Caucasian, likely to be divorced or single, likely to be unemployed, living in low household incomes, and likely to be uninsured (Mengling et al., 2011; Washington et al., 2007, 2011). Using a nationally representative sample, Vogt and colleagues (2006) found women VA users with a service-connected disabilities endured greater challenges with ease of using facilities, in addition to availability of services than WV with non-service connected disabilities. Lairson and colleagues (2005) showed that WVs 50 years and older, who were smokers and in poor health status were less likely to get breast screenings, while those with more years of education, insurance, higher income, and an individual belief of supposed risk were more likely to get screened.

Access to and Perceptions of Care

General access barriers for WVs included lower income, greater distance from mammography imaging center, lack of knowledge about specific health services (Mengling et al., 2011; Washington et al., 2006, 2011), longer waiting times to get care, and lack of continuity of care (Vogt et al., 2006).

Perceptions of VHA care sometimes depended on utilization of services, what someone heard about the care, and lack of information about the ability to receive services (different from lack of knowledge of women specific services). In general, WVs lack information about eligibility and availability of services, want sensitive quality care related to women's health issues, and feel they are subjected to a male-dominated atmosphere (Mengeling et al., 2011; Vogt et al., 2006; Washington et al., 2006, 2007, 2011). Furthermore, accessibility to women providers, child care, location, distance and

ease of making appointments, and wait time were also important aspects about their perception of quality of care and decision-making about VA use. Lastly, lack of after-hours access to nonemergency care was also a reason for why WVs use outside healthcare (Washington et al., 2006).

Evidence-based Recommendations

To effectively influence breast screening adherence rates, key determinants can be identified to match organizational need. These led to the following recommendations for mammography programs: (a) know the current practice processes and available resources, (b) know the makeup of the target population (socio-demographics), (c) research local needs, and (d) consider local and nonlocal evidence regarding the usefulness of different interventions (Baron, 2010; CPSTF, 2012; Sabatino et al., 2012). The Task Force on Community Preventive Services (TFCPS), an independent, nonfederal task force, published its most recent systematic review, *The Guide to Community Preventive Services (Community Guide)*, identifying evidence-based population health interventions to decrease mortality rates, increase life expectancy, and improve quality of life. This source provides recommendations to assist providers in federal, state, and local health departments make informed practice decisions.

The TFCPS systematic review findings include *client-oriented* and *provider-oriented* strategies. The following *client-oriented* screening intervention strategies increase breast screening rates: (a) client reminders, (b) small media (e.g., videos, print materials such as brochures, letters, and newsletters), (c) lessening of structural barriers and simplifying administrative procedures (e.g., reducing time, decreasing distance, modifying hours of operations, offering mobile mammography, scheduling assistance,

dependent care, transportation, patient navigators, etc.), (d) personalized education, (e) group education, and (f) reduction of out-of-pocket costs (Baron et al., 2010; CPSTF, 2012; Sabatino et al., 2012). In addition, they also reported a strong evidence base for provider reminders, recall systems, provider assessments and feedback as intervention strategies focused on *providers*. Ratings for the aforementioned strategies were categorized as strong or had satisfactory evidence that the intervention is effective. Intervention strategies that did not have sufficient evidence and/or where the evidence was weak included: (a) client incentives, (b) mass media, (c) provider incentives, and (d) encouraging informed decision making for breast cancer screenings (CPSTF).

In the first study of WVs regarding breast screening behaviors, Hynes and colleagues (1998) found that WVs are at high-risk for poor health behaviors. The authors looked at predictors of mammography while controlling for race, age, military service time, and VA user status. They found that WVs who were “told” to have a mammogram by a provider or a nurse were five times more likely (*OR* 5.41, *CI* 4.63-6.32) to have ever had breast cancer screening and nearly twice as likely (*OR* 1.81, *CI* 1.57-2.09) to have had breast cancer screening within the last two years as compared to those who were “not.” Similarly, Baron and colleagues (2010) found strong evidence that a healthcare professional reminder call improves mammography screenings in their more recent study. Hynes and colleagues (1998) also reported that WVs who have served greater than 9.5 years are three times more likely to have a preventive screening than those who have served less time in the military.

Studies of organizational or community interventions to increase mammography screening rates have documented several successful strategies. Two systematic reviews

reported strong/robust support for client prompts (Baron et al., 2012; Sabatino et al., 2012) while Sabatino et al. found strong/robust evidence for individual education, reducing personal costs for screening, and decreasing structural barriers. In a pragmatic randomized trial of 1000+ women in an urban federal-designated underserved area, Fortuna et al. (2013) found that both personalized outreach and directed in-reach (provider prompt) doubled the odds of screening rates over a reminder letter alone. In a national German breast screening initiative including almost 5500 women (Hegenscheid et al., 2011), the attendance rates among the intervention group (29.7%) and the control group (26.1%) showed more of an increase when the women were sent a second reminder in addition to receiving telephone counseling, showing the benefit of including telephone counseling along with a written reminder. In a randomized controlled trial of 700+ women Veterans (Dalessandri et al., 1998), having a nurse follow up call to schedule the mammogram and answer questions resulted in 5-fold increase in 6-month mammography rates compared to women who only received a mailed informational letter/brochure. Despite the method, breast screening rates remained low in these studies with no screening rates higher than 40% of targeted women.

Hegenscheid and colleagues (2011) followed up their interventions with a satisfaction survey and the results showed that 33% of German women stated that the personal counseling influenced their decision to complete a breast screening, 56% reported that they actually received their breast screening, and 77% approved of the telephone counseling that could be used to motivate non-responders. Baron et al. (2010) and Lairson et al. (2005) also reported that a discussion between the healthcare

professional and the patient regarding the importance of breast cancer screening can be an important factor of compliance with screening recommendations.

Use of a Population-based Database to Improve Adherence

Unless appropriate changes are made in management of breast screenings and follow-ups, there will continue to be variations in performance measures and the potential for missed follow-ups that can lead to delayed care and treatment. Missed follow-ups of abnormal mammograms is a quality of care issue (Taplin et al., 2004). An additional literature search and review was conducted in order to explore the benefits of developing and utilizing a population-based database for the WHC at the large federal HCS.

The evidence shows that clinical reminders used to support providers at point of care have aided in improving performance measure compliance (Lester et al., 2009), yet it has also been reported that with the competing clinical demands and the increased number of performance measures that they can also be underutilized. Additionally the authors reported that the point of care reminders were also associated with minimal improvement in meeting the measures.

According to the *Medical Dictionary for the Health Professions and Nursing* (2012) “registries” are databases of patients who share a specific characteristic and can be classified according to how their populations are defined (cancer, trauma, implants, etc.). Databases are a computerized method of collecting data that can be used for auditing, monitoring, and tracking. According to the Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality (AHRQ), the WHC database would be considered a health services database because of its purpose of addressing either clinical encounters or procedures like mammography (Gliklich & Dreyer, 2010). Such databases can identify sub-population patients for

proactive care, including timely preventive care (e.g., at appropriate intervals). In addition, they can allow tracking of abnormal follow-ups and provide queries and reports to facilitate communication, thus, improving patient safety and quality of care (American College of Obstetricians and Gynecologists, 2012; Corkery, 2007; Lester et al., 2009; Osuch, et al., 1995; Taplin, et al., 2004).

METHODS

Setting

The practice setting was a women's health clinic which included two RN care managers, three LVNs, one clerk, two Physicians, and one NP that is located within a large teaching VA hospital, located in Southern California. This hospital system is part of network of facilities which includes four other VA facilities. There are 304 hospital beds, 110 nursing beds for a total of 414 operating beds as of FY2013. In addition to the main campus, there are five CBOCs where WV receive their primary and preventive care. However, the only mammography center is located at the main hospital in a city that is not central to all the CBOCs (Cabrillo – 7 miles, Whittier/Santa Fe Springs – 16 miles, Santa Ana – 20 miles, Anaheim – 22 miles, and Laguna Hills – 33 miles).

Strategies used to reach project goals included:

1. Identified and included stakeholders from the WHC (providers, nurse supervisor, women's health program coordinator, nursing staff, and ancillary staff), including radiology. This effort fostered investment in the project and overcame potential resistance to change.
2. Defined the population (national guidelines, target population eligible)
3. Convened a meeting in September 2014 with stakeholders to discuss current referral, screening, and follow-up processes and created a screening process flow map (Appendix B) that identified potential for communication gaps during care delivery and or at transitions in care, which were considered in the development of the database to address those gaps.

4. Established a collaborative relationship with the primary care management analyst who provided technical support through meetings as needed. In addition to technical support the management analyst also agreed to take ownership and management of the product when implemented.
5. Decided on a timeline to measure progress while working with the clinic leadership and project team.
6. Reviewed monthly progress with project team to monitor status of database development beginning October 2014 to March 2015.
7. Worked closely with the primary care manager (designated nurse covering the mammography program within WHC) to provide feedback on the content, visuals and usability of the database.

Description of Project

Software Description

Microsoft Access, also known as Microsoft Office Access, is a database management system from Microsoft that combines the relational (organizes data into one or more tables (or "relations") of rows and columns, with a unique key for each row) Microsoft Jet Database Engine (an underlying component of a database, a collection of information stored on a computer in a systematic way) with a graphical user interface (a type of interface that allows users to interact with electronic devices through graphical icons and visual indicators such as secondary notation, as opposed to text-based interfaces, typed command labels or text navigation) and software-development tools. It can import or link directly to data stored in other applications and databases. Users can create tables, queries, forms and reports, and connect them together with macros (Fuller

& Cook, 2013; Microsoft Access, n.d.). Additional Access qualities include the ability to be utilized by multiple users concurrently versus the single user Excel spreadsheet and ease of use. This project will use the Microsoft Access 2013 version.

Features of the Database

To develop an effective evidence-based database tool, a literature search and synthesis was conducted that identified relevant attributes and possible contributing factors that can impact the care management and success of a mammography program. In collaboration with the WHC care managers and the primary care management analyst, the author selected key data fields and defined the purpose of each (Figure 2). The goal of the mammography database was to pre-populate as much as possible with information from the EHR. Some data elements will need to be manually entered by RN care managers, LVNs, clinic clerks, or providers.

The development of the database involved considerations about workload and decisions to be sure it was integrated into the current daily work of staff (Corkery, 2007), saving time and allowing access to daily updated data. Hortman and Thompson (2005) defined usability of a system by its functionality and ease of use. To be of maximal value, a system will be easy to use, and meet the needs of the end user. It can provide a comprehensive picture of practice patterns, along with detailed reports and graphs. Basically, the goals of a newly designed system should be to reduce visual, intellectual, memory, and motor work and ultimately, to remove any feelings of more work imposed by the new technology (Hortman & Thompson).

Data Field	Description
Navigation Screen (Default) (See Appendix C)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provides the user with a snap shot of the WVs demographics and current mammography reminder • Tabs provide the user a way to bring a section to the front without having to the leave the main screen • Within the navigation bar are buttons that access updated reports as needed
(Screen Shot 1) Demographics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Confirms correct patient and contact information • Confirms assignment of Primary Care Provider • Provides an opportunity to ask the WV if they would like to receive reminders and/or health and wellness information via email
(Screen Shot 2) Mammography Reminder (Tab One)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provides due date • Determines if WV received a mammogram outside of the VA and provides an opportunity to confirm date and location • Track dates Mammography ordered and completed • Determines deferral reason • Determines readiness to get mammography screening
(Screen Shot 3) Notification Attempts (Tab Two)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tracks dates of phone call attempts • Tracks dates of reminder letters sent • Links to telephone scripts • Links to ready to print reminder letters
(Screen Shot 4) Abnormal Mammograms (Tab Three)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provides BI-RADS (Breast Imaging-Reporting Data System) results • Confirm need for additional views • Track dates biopsy ordered and completed • Provides biopsy results • Confirm need for breast clinic referral • Links to VHA and local policy, references, resources
(Screen Shot 5) Notes (Tab Four)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Internal communication tool for approved end-users
Search Tool	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provides a quick way to locate the WVs record by typing in the last name
Print Record Button	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provides only a copy of the current demographic record and current tab
Close Data Entry Form Button	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Closes only the current record
Finish Button	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Close entire database and prompts user to save any changes

Figure 2. Mammography Access database fields and purpose.

The mammography database is intended to allow WHC user to have immediate access to key information related to WV mammography status in one screen versus taking time to search through multiple sections in CPRS. There are a number of valuable queries and audits that can be accessed, but not limited to the following examples: mammography due dates to initiate reminder letters or calls, a list of reasons for denials and readiness to get a mammography in planning for appropriate interventions, zip codes of WV residences to assess potential distance barrier to the clinic for a mammography, and finally dates of birth by month to send an “It’s Your Birthday” with wellness wishes from the WHC and reminders about prevention screenings for their age decade including health and wellness tips, which in turn supports the patient-centered philosophy of the federal HCS. Tracking and trending reports, but not limited to the following are: viewing the provider’s panels and completions rates, review of ordering and mammography completion rates, including compliance with notification requirements of abnormal results and follow-ups. The results from the tracking and trending provide a cyclic quality improvement process that includes entering data, benchmarking, analyzing and developing and implementing any necessary improvement plan.

Database Support

The Microsoft Access tracking database will be located in the WHC secured network shared drive, which provides for the security of data information behind the agency firewall, as the access can be limited to only those given permission. The management analyst will play a significant role in the importing of actual patient data from the regional data warehouse (RDW) into the Access database including writing the programming that will link the database to the RDW for nightly updates. This can keep

the database current, ensuring the consistency of data sought (e.g., adding new patients, hiding expired patients, updating reminders, and any other data element that can be linked to the RDW).

Implementation Plan

The database pilot will occur in the WHC and one of the five CBOCs (Figure 3). A mock mammography database copy will be used for training. Training will occur in phases by utilization need (RN care managers, LVNs, clerks, and then, providers). Permissions to shared drive will need to be confirmed. The mammography database introduction training will be provided by the author in multiple scheduled presentations that will include the following:

- Explaining the need that prompted development of an evidence-based supported database,
- Addressing the benefits of design and content collaboration driven by the nurses,
- Reassuring and demonstrating how it was integrated into current workload,
- Defining the potential quality improvement goal outcomes, and
- Reflecting on how it supports patient-centered health and wellness to improve WV satisfaction.

The hands on mammography database training will be completed in the computer lab, in addition to one-on-one support that will include: a tour of the database, data entry, running reports, accessing links, printing embedded letters and trouble shooting. A handbook with screenshots of the database will also be included to provide step by step instructions and who to contact if something is wrong.

Figure 3. Implementation timeline.

Evaluation

Upon database completion, the next step is “Do” in the FOCUS-PDCA model. This will be to pilot the product in the WHC. Hortman and colleagues (2005) defined five quality components to consider when evaluating how easy a database design is functionally. They include (1) learnability, (2) efficiency, (3) memorability, (4) errors and (5) satisfaction.

It will be important during the pilot phase to listen for what the end users say and observe their success or difficulty with product. This will be done during the “Check” step, along with comparing current data to predicted outcomes and previous benchmarks for the national EPRP measures (collected prior to implementation). To assess user satisfaction, a survey tool will be used. The Questionnaire for User Interaction Satisfaction (QUIS) Version 7.0 is a 12-part questionnaire with multiple questions in

each part that was developed by a multi-disciplinary team to assess users' subjective satisfaction with specific aspects of a software program (Appendix D). The QUIS licensing agreement has been obtained and includes the paper document (Appendix E) which includes a demographic questionnaire and uses six scales to measure overall system satisfaction and nine specific interface factors (screen factors, terminology and system information, learning, system capabilities, technical manuals and on-line help, on-line tutorials, multimedia, teleconferencing, software installation).

A formal evaluation of the database is important to support changes during the performance improvement cycle. Until the results of the planned changes are accepted and full implementation occurs then the team will skip the "Act" phase and return to the "Plan" to make changes in the database and repeat the cycle.

Implications for Practice

Research has suggested that implementing proven evidence-based strategies that improve women's breast screening adherence rates could potentially reduce the mortality and morbidity of breast cancer through early discovery, when treatment is more likely to be helpful (Baron et al., 2010; CPSTF, 2012; Dalessandri, et al, 1998; Fortuna et al., 2013; Hegenscheid et al., 2011; Hynes et al., 1998; Sabatino et al., 2012). Furthermore, standardizing this federal HCS practice can lead to continuity of prevention screening across this organization and decrease missed opportunities for timely completion of mammography (Edgar et al., 2013; Lairson et al., 2005; Mengeling et al., 2011; Vogt et al., 2006; Washington et al., 2006, 2007, 2011). Evidence of improvements in mammography rates should be observed in the future EPRP reports; after introduction of

the mammography Microsoft Access database for regular reminders for screening and follow-ups.

CONCLUSION

As our nation's heroes, WVs deserve and have earned the right to the best healthcare access that our VHA system of care can provide for their contributions and sacrifices for family and nation. Increases in numbers of WVs accessing VHA care make it important to deliver timely services attentive to women's health needs. This may include prevention screenings, wellness and reproductive health, mental health, geriatric and perhaps extended care. This large federal HCS did not meet its FY 2013 mammography performance measures. It was time for action and as a WV who receives care within this HCS, it became evident to me that this was my opportunity to improve an area of nursing practice that I felt passionate about and which affected outcomes for WVs as well as myself. It was my commitment to WV quality and satisfaction with care that drove this doctoral project.

Mammography performance measures should be improved by implementing the newly developed user-friendly database tracking tool. The FOCUS-PDCA model provided a useful framework in developing the Microsoft Access database tool that focuses on the mammography screening process, the needs of WVs, and the wants of the end users. The RN Care Managers, LVNs, Providers and office staff need an effective way to communicate, coordinate and follow-up on WV preventive screenings and results.

It is anticipated that the database will directly impact and improve the organization's mammography performance measures, while enhancing WV and staff satisfaction. Improving access to care and adherence to guidelines using this database are

only a part of the management of this special group of Veterans. In the future, it is hoped that information about WVs as related to additional screening measures (pap smear and colonoscopy) may be added to the database. This would show its utility.

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APPENDIX A

FOCUS-PDSA FRAMEWORK PERMISSION EMAIL

RE: Request for permission to use Intellectual Property

From: **Alexander, Miles** (MAlexander@kilpatricktownsend.com)

Sent: Mon 3/03/14 8:27 AM

To: Yvonne Ginez-Gonzales (yvonnegonzalesrn@hotmail.com)

Good morning – wish I could help but we no longer handle trademark matters for this client and I do not know who does so. I do not believe that HCA has a client of our firm for many years.

Sincerely,

Miles

Miles Alexander

Kilpatrick Townsend & Stockton LLP

Suite 2800 | 1100 Peachtree Street NE | Atlanta, GA 30309-4528

office 404 815 6410 | cell 404 394 4649 | fax 404 541 3105

malexander@kilpatricktownsend.com | [My Profile](#) | [vCard](#)

From: Yvonne Ginez-Gonzales [mailto:yvonnegonzalesrn@hotmail.com]

Sent: Sunday, March 02, 2014 6:59 PM

To: Alexander, Miles

Subject: Request for permission to use Intellectual Property

Good evening Mr. Alexander,

My name is Yvonne Ginez-Gonzales. I located your name at the website Legal Force - Trademarkia as the correspondent for the FOCUS-PDCA model. I am a first year student at California State University, Fullerton (CSUF) in their Doctorate of Nursing Practice (DNP) program. I will be participating in and leading a performance improvement project at VA Long Beach Healthcare System in California, where I am employed. The purpose for my email is to request permission for use of the FOCUS-PDCA model that is trademarked by the Hospital Corporation of America. During my literature review for my project which focuses on improving the breast cancer screening adherence rates for our women veterans, I came across the FOCUS-PDCA model and believe it meets the needs of my project. VA Long Beach currently utilizes Deming's PDCA model and has adopted it for all of its performance improvement projects. However, I appreciate the adaptation of the FOCUS methodology that was utilized in an article called The FOCUS-PDCA Strategy by a number of editors Merritt and colleagues located at <http://centralstatehospital.org/policy/plan8.10A.pdf>. In order to move forward with my project and to go to defense I need an official notification that I have permission to utilize this model in my project. If you have any questions, please do not hesitate to contact me

at Yvonnegonzalesrn@hotmail.com. I look forward to your response that I may move forward in a timely manner with my project deadline.

Respectfully yours,

Yvonne Ginez-Gonzales, MSN, RN, NE-BC
Doctorate of Nursing Practice Student

Confidentiality Notice:

This communication constitutes an electronic communication within the meaning of the Electronic Communications Privacy Act, 18 U.S.C. Section 2510, and its disclosure is strictly limited to the recipient intended by the sender of this message. This transmission, and any attachments, may contain confidential attorney-client privileged information and attorney work product. If you are not the intended recipient, any disclosure, copying, distribution or use of any of the information contained in or attached to this transmission is STRICTLY PROHIBITED. Please contact us immediately by return e-mail or at 404 815 6500, and destroy the original transmission and its attachments without reading or saving in any manner.

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APPENDIX B

SCREENING PROCESS FLOW MAP

APPENDIX C

MICROSOFT ACCESS MAMMOGRAPHY DATABASE SCREEN SHOTS

Navigation Form

VA Long Beach Mammography Database

WHC - MammoDataBase
Mammography Due List

VA Long Beach Healthcare System Mammography Database
"When breast cancer is detected early, in the localized stage, the 5-year survival rate is 98%."
National Cancer Institute

SEARCH

DEMOGRAPHICS **1**

Last, First Name: Alsop Theresa MI B
Last4 SSN: 3456 DOB: 4/19/1960 Age: 54 Provider: Hernandez, Sofia
Street Address: 2015 Awesome Way City: Whittier State: CA Zip Code: 90601
Home: (562) 345-1456 Email Address: theresa.alsop@schoolproject.com
Cell: (562) 345-1456 Would you like to receive health information from the WHC to your email? Yes No
Work: (562) 345-1456 Would you like to receive health prevention screening reminders from the WHC to your email? Yes No

****IMPORTANT****
This database does not document in CPRS.
Required documentation will need to be entered directly in to CPRS.

PRINT RECORD
CLOSE DATA ENTRY FORM
FINISH

Mammography Reminder Notification Attempts Abnormal Mammogram F/U Notes

Mammography Due Date Deferral Reasons
5/15/2015 Informed Refusal
 Received Other Location Other - Deferral Reason

Mammography Reminder Notification Attempts Abnormal Mammogram F/U Notes

Mammography Due Date **2**
3/27/2015 Deferral Reasons
 Received Other Location Mammography Scheduled
Date Received at Other Location Other - Deferral Reason
Mammography Ordered Date: 2/27/2015 *Readiness To Get Mammography Screening
Definite Yes - planning soon and can set date
Mammogram Completed Date: 3/13/2015 Other - Readiness To Get Mammography Screening Reason

*Costanza, M. E., Luckmann, R., White, M. J., Rosa, M. C., Cranos, C., Reed, G., ... Yood, R. (2011). Design and methods for a randomized clinical trial comparing three outreach efforts to improve screening mammography adherence. BMC Health Services Research, 11(1), 145. doi: 10.1186/1472-6963-11-145.

Mammography Reminder	Notification Attempts	Abnormal Mammogram F/U	Notes
3			
Reminder Letters Sent 1st <input type="text" value="1/27/2015"/> <input type="text" value="Mammography Education Handout"/> 2nd <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/> 3rd <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/>		REMINDER AND FOLLOW-UP LETTERS Mammography Reminder Letter Mammography Tailored Reminder Letter (No family History and Dislikes Going to MD Appts.)	
Phone Call Attempts 1st <input type="text" value="2/12/2015"/> <input type="text" value="Left Voicemail to Return Call"/> 2nd <input type="text" value="2/20/2015"/> <input type="text" value="Spoke with Woman Veteran"/> 3rd <input type="text"/> <input type="text"/>		EDUCATIONAL RESOURCES Mammography Education Handout Feb 2015	
		BIRTHDAY REMINDERS LETTERS Birthday reminder 20-29 Birthday reminder 30-39 Birthday reminder 40-49 Birthday reminder 50-65 Birthday reminder over 65	

Mammography Reminder	Notification Attempts	Abnormal Mammogram F/U	Notes
4			
BI-RADS (Breast Imaging-Reporting Data System) <input type="text" value="5 = Highly suspicious of malignancy"/>		HSP 11-12 Health Care for Women Veterans Guidelines Normal Results - Communicated within 14 business days from the date of the report becoming available "Suspicious Abnormality" or "Highly Suspicious of Malignancy" - the lay summary results and recommended course of action should be communicated to the patient as soon as possible but no later than 5 business days after the mammogram. NOTE: Prompt verbal communication does not obviate the need to also provide written communication to the patient within 30 calendar days of the date of the mammogram	
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Additional Views Ordered			
Breast Biopsy F/U Date <input type="text" value="2/24/2015"/>			
Breast Biopsy F/U Completed Date <input type="text" value="3/3/2015"/>			
Breast Biopsy Results <input type="text" value="Abnormal"/>			
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Breast Clinic Referral			
		References and Resources HSP 11-12 Health Care for Women Veterans VHA Handbook 1105.03 Mammography Program Procedures and Standards Center for Women Veterans Home American Cancer Society - Breast U.S. Preventive Services Task Force (USPSTF) - Breast Cancer	

Mammography Reminder	Notification Attempts	Abnormal Mammogram F/U	Notes	FINISH
			<p>1.9.15 Called pt. to f/u on reminder letter. Stated she did not drive anymore and she did not have anyone to bring her. Contacted SW to set up transportation with Secure Transport on 2.10.15. YGG</p> <p>2.21.14 Called pt. to schedule for a biopsy due to Bi-Rads results. Scheduled for 2.24.15. YGG</p>	

APPENDIX D

REQUEST FOR QUIS USE PERMISSION

Yvonne Ginez-Gonzales <yvonnegonzalesrn@csu.fullerton.edu>

Request QUIS use permission for Doctoral Project

4 messages

Yvonne Ginez-Gonzales <yvonnegonzalesrn@csu.fullerton.edu>
Tue, Feb 10, 2015 at
10:23 AMTo: ben@cs.umd.edu

Greetings Dr. Shneiderman,

My name is Yvonne Ginez-Gonzales and I am a Doctor of Nursing Practice student at California State University, Fullerton with an expected graduation date of May 2015. I am requesting to permission to use your long form and short form paper versions of QUIS. I did go online and sign the licensing agreement and have access, but would like to have an email acknowledgement for my paper.

I came across your questionnaire doing research for my DNP project in a paper by, Hortman, P. A., & Thompson, C. B. (2005). Evaluation of user interface satisfaction of a clinical outcomes database. *Computers Informatics Nursing*, 23(6), 301-307.

I work at VA Long Beach Healthcare System in Long Beach, CA and have almost completed my Microsoft Access 2013 database that I would like to pilot and implement to track our women Veterans Mammography compliance and follow-up. The end-users are in our Women's Health Clinic and have been included with the development from the beginning providing content and design suggestions.

I would like to be able to evaluate their satisfaction after piloting and again after full implementation. I believe your questionnaire tool can be of value. I also wanted to know if you have a paper that provides the reliability and validity of questions. Finally, do you require additional permission request if I would like to omit questions that I do not feel meet the need of the information sought?

Thank you for you time to address my request and questions. I look forward to your email.

Respectfully yours,

Yvonne Ginez-Gonzales, MSN, RN, NE-BC

yvonnegonzalesrn@csu.fullerton.edu

Ben Shneiderman <ben@cs.umd.edu>

Tue, Feb 10, 2015 at 10:31 AM

To: Yvonne Ginez-Gonzales <yvonnegonzalesrn@csu.fullerton.edu>

Cc: "Kent L. Norman (klnorman@umd.edu)" <klnorman@umd.edu>

Thanks for your interest... I am copying to my colleague Kent Norman, who handles these requests....

I saw your earlier note,... so I am using a different email to reach Prof. Norman ...
Best wishes... Ben Shneiderman

From: Yvonne Ginez-Gonzales [mailto:yvonnegonzalesrn@csu.fullerton.edu]

Sent: Tuesday, February 10, 2015 1:23 PM

To: Ben Shneiderman

Subject: Request QUIIS use permission for Doctoral Project

Kent L. Norman <klnorman@umd.edu>

Thu, Feb 12, 2015 at 10:34 AM

To: Yvonne Ginez-Gonzales <yvonnegonzalesrn@csu.fullerton.edu>

Cc: bshneide-contact <BEN@cs.umd.edu>

Dear Yvonne:

Your email was forwarded to me from Dr. Shneiderman.

Technically you need to license the use of QUIIS through

Office of Technology Commercialization

Attention: Dan Eastman (Administrative Assistant)

The University of Maryland

2130 Mitchell Building

College Park, MD 20742-5213

(301) 405-3947

(301) 314-9502 (fax)

otc@umd.edu

If you go to <http://lap.umd.edu/quis/> you will find information and papers on the reliability and validity of the QUIIS under Technical Support and References.

There is no problem adding and omitting some questions as you wish.

Sounds like a great project.

Best wishes in your research and study.

Kent

Dr. Kent L. Norman, Associate Professor
Department of Psychology, University of Maryland
College Park, MD 20742
Tel: (301) 405-5924
Fax: (301) 314-9566

Email: klnorman@umd.edu

Laboratory for Automation Psychology:

<http://lap.umd.edu>
 Human-Computer Interaction Laboratory:
<http://www.cs.umd.edu/hcil>
 Web courses:
<http://cognitron.umd.edu/>

Cyberpsychology: An Introduction to the Psychology of Human-Computer Interaction
<http://www.cambridge.org/us/catalogue/catalogue.asp?isbn=9780521687027>

Yvonne Ginez-Gonzales

<yvonnegonzalesrn@csu.fullerton.edu>

Thu, Feb 12, 2015 at 11:43 AM

To: otc@umd.edu

Dear Mr. Eastman,

I have been forwarded your name from Dr. Norman to request permission for use of QUIS tool. Please see purpose in previous emails below. I have to submit my paper to my committee reader next week and hope to hear from you before then. If you have any questions please contact me at my email Yvonnegonzalesrn@csu.fullerton.edu. I look forward to your response.

Respectfully your,

Yvonne Ginez-Gonzales, MSN, RN, NE-BC

CSUF DNP Student

[Quoted text hidden]

--

Yvonne Ginez-Gonzales

Yvonne Ginez-Gonzales

<yvonnegonzalesrn@csu.fullerton.edu>

QUIS Licensing information

1 message

Daniel Benedict Eastman <dbeastma@umd.edu>

Thu, Feb 12, 2015 at 12:37 PM

To: "Yvonnegonzalesrn@csu.fullerton.edu" <Yvonnegonzalesrn@csu.fullerton.edu>

Ms. Ginez-Gonzales,

In response to your questions regarding QUIS 7.0 (Questionnaire for User Interaction Satisfaction), the pricing for a site license is as follows:

Student Paper Version: \$ 50.00 // Web version free with purchase of paper version

***Note that the Web Version no longer has any technical support from its creators, so it will be free with the purchase of the paper version.**

You may pay using a **check** (payment in U.S. dollars, drawn on a U.S. bank, made payable to the University of Maryland and mailed to the address below), **purchase order** (mailed or faxed) or a **credit card**. We do not currently accept wire transfers. If you pay with a credit card, we need the following information (faxed, phoned or e-mailed):

- Card name (Visa, Mastercard or Discover)
- Card number
- Card expiration date
- Exact name on the card
- Billing address

A unique User ID and Password will be **mailed** as soon as the check clears or the credit card has been approved by the campus business office. Please visit the QUIS website for additional information at: <http://lap.umd.edu/quis>

This procedure should take a week or less. If you need your purchase expedited, let me know and I can send you your username and password on receipt of your payment information.

If you have any questions please do not hesitate to contact us. Also, you may visit our web site at www.otc.umd.edu.

Thank you.

Dan Eastman, Admin Assistant
University of Maryland
Office of Technology Commercialization
2130 Mitchell Building
College Park, MD 20742
301-405-3947
FAX: 301-314-9502

APPENDIX E

QUISTM LICENSE AGREEMENT AND QUESTIONNAIRE

1. Definitions: "QUISTM" means the "Questionnaire for User Interaction Satisfaction" (Copyright © 1984, 1993, 1998. University of Maryland. All rights reserved.). "Licensed Materials" means the electronic and paper versions of QUISTM and all documentation included in this package and any modifications or updates of said materials delivered to Licensee. "Licensor" means the University of Maryland. "Licensee" means the individual or organization licensing and opening this package.

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7.2 Termination of this agreement shall not relieve either party of the obligations arising hereunder before termination. Upon termination, Licensee must return, or certify the destruction of (and erasure from any storage device), all copies of the Licensed Materials.

8. General:

8.1 It is agreed that the laws of the State of Maryland will govern without reference to conflict of law principles. Any and all legal actions must be brought in the courts in the State of Maryland or in the U.S. District Court for the District of Maryland. Licensee consents to the jurisdiction of said courts.

8.2 No modification of this Agreement shall be binding unless it is written and signed by an authorized representative of the party against whom enforcement of the modification is sought.

8.3 Neither this Agreement, the License granted hereby, nor any part thereof may be assigned or otherwise transferred by Licensee.

8.4 In the event that any of the terms of this Agreement is, or becomes, or is declared to be invalid or void by any court or tribunal of competent jurisdiction, such term or terms shall be null and void and shall be deemed severed from this Agreement and all the remaining terms of this Agreement shall remain in full force and effect.

8.5 No action, regardless of form, arising out of this Agreement, except an action by the University of Maryland for enforcement of its intellectual property rights or damages resulting from Licensee's breach thereof, may be brought by either party more than one (1) year after the cause of action has arisen.

Should you have any questions concerning this Agreement, or if you wish to contact the University of Maryland for any reason, please write:

Office of Technology Commercialization
University of Maryland
0133 Cole Student Activities Building
College Park, MD 20742-1001

QUESTIONNAIRE FOR USER INTERACTION SATISFACTION (QUIS)

SHORT VERSION 7.0

Identification number: _____
System code: _____
Age: _____
Gender: _____ **male**
 _____ **female**

PART 1: System Experience

1.1 How long have you worked on this system?

- | | |
|--|---|
| <input type="checkbox"/> less than 1 hour | <input type="checkbox"/> 6 months to less than 1 year |
| <input type="checkbox"/> 1 hour to less than 1 day | <input type="checkbox"/> 1 year to less than 2 years |
| <input type="checkbox"/> 1 day to less than 1 week | <input type="checkbox"/> 2 years to less than 3 years |
| <input type="checkbox"/> 1 week to less than 1 month | <input type="checkbox"/> 3 years or more |
| <input type="checkbox"/> 1 month to less than 6 months | |

1.2 On the average, how much time do you spend per week on this system?

- | | |
|---|--|
| <input type="checkbox"/> less than one hour | <input type="checkbox"/> 4 to less than 10 hours |
| <input type="checkbox"/> one to less than 4 hours | <input type="checkbox"/> over 10 hours |

PART 2: Past Experience

2.1 How many operating systems have you worked with?

- | | |
|-------------------------------|--------------------------------------|
| <input type="checkbox"/> none | <input type="checkbox"/> 3-4 |
| <input type="checkbox"/> 1 | <input type="checkbox"/> 5-6 |
| <input type="checkbox"/> 2 | <input type="checkbox"/> more than 6 |

2.2 Of the following devices, software, and systems, check those that you have personally used and are familiar with:

- | | | |
|--|---|--|
| <input type="checkbox"/> computer terminal | <input type="checkbox"/> joy stick | <input type="checkbox"/> computer games |
| <input type="checkbox"/> personal computer | <input type="checkbox"/> pen based computing | <input type="checkbox"/> voice recognition |
| <input type="checkbox"/> lap top computer | <input type="checkbox"/> graphics tablet | <input type="checkbox"/> video editing systems |
| <input type="checkbox"/> color monitor | <input type="checkbox"/> head mounted display | <input type="checkbox"/> CAD computer aided design |
| <input type="checkbox"/> touch screen | <input type="checkbox"/> modems | <input type="checkbox"/> rapid prototyping systems |
| <input type="checkbox"/> floppy drive | <input type="checkbox"/> scanners | <input type="checkbox"/> e-mail |
| <input type="checkbox"/> CD-ROM drive | <input type="checkbox"/> word processor | <input type="checkbox"/> internet |
| <input type="checkbox"/> keyboard | <input type="checkbox"/> graphics software | |
| <input type="checkbox"/> mouse | <input type="checkbox"/> spreadsheet software | |
| <input type="checkbox"/> track ball | <input type="checkbox"/> database software | |

PART 3: Overall User Reactions

Please circle the numbers which most appropriately reflect your impressions about using this computer system. Not Applicable = NA.

3.1	Overall reactions to the system:	terrible 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9	wonderful	NA
3.2		frustrating 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9	satisfying	NA
3.3		dull 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9	stimulating	NA
3.4		difficult 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9	easy	NA
3.5		inadequate power 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9	adequate power	NA
3.6		rigid 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9	flexible	NA

PART 4: Screen

4.1	Characters on the computer screen	hard to read 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9	easy to read	NA
4.2	Highlighting on the screen	unhelpful 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9	helpful	NA
4.3	Screen layouts were helpful	never 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9	always	NA
4.4	Sequence of screens	confusing 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9	clear	NA

Please write your comments about the screens here:

PART 5: Terminology and System Information

5.1 Use of terminology throughout system	inconsistent 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9	consistent	NA
5.2 Terminology relates well to the work you are doing?	never 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9	always	NA
5.3 Messages which appear on screen	inconsistent 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9	consistent	NA
5.4 Messages which appear on screen	confusing 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9	clear	NA
5.5 Computer keeps you informed about what it is doing	never 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9	always	NA
5.6 Error messages	unhelpful 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9	helpful	NA

Please write your comments about terminology and system information here:

PART 6: Learning

6.1 Learning to operate the system	difficult 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9	easy	NA
6.2 Exploration of features by trial and error	discouraging 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9	encouraging	NA
6.3 Remembering names and use of commands	difficult 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9	easy	NA
6.4 Tasks can be performed in a straight-forward manner	never 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9	always	NA

Please write your comments about learning here:

PART 7: System Capabilities

7.1 System speed	too slow 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9	fast enough	NA
7.2 The system is reliable	never 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9	always	NA
7.3 System tends to be	noisy 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9	quiet	NA
7.4 Correcting your mistakes	difficult 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9	easy	NA
7.5 Ease of operation depends on your level of experience	never 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9	always	NA

Please write your comments about system capabilities here:

PART 8: Technical Manuals and On-line help

8.1 Technical manuals are	confusing 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9	clear	NA
8.2 Information from the manual is easily understood	never 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9	always	NA
8.3 Amount of help given	inadequate 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9	adequate	NA

Please write your comments about technical manuals and on-line help here:

PART 9: On-line Tutorials

9.1 Tutorial was	useless 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9	helpful	NA
9.2 Maneuvering through the tutorial was	difficult 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9	easy	NA
9.3 Tutorial content was	useless 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9	helpful	NA
9.4 Tasks can be completed	with difficulty 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9	easily	NA
9.5 Learning to operate the system using the tutorial was	difficult 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9	easy	NA

Please write your comments about on-line tutorials here:

PART 10: Multimedia

10.1 Quality of still pictures/photographs	bad 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9	good	NA
10.2 Quality of movies	bad 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9	good	NA
10.3 Sound output	inaudible 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9	audible	NA
10.4 Colors used are	unnatural 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9	natural	NA

Please write your comments about multimedia here:

PART 11: Teleconferencing

11.1	Setting up for conference	difficult 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9	easy 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9	NA
11.2	Arrangement of windows showing connecting groups	confusing 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9	clear 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9	NA
11.3	Determining the focus of attention during conference was	confusing 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9	clear 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9	NA
11.4	Video image flow	choppy 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9	smooth 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9	NA
11.5	Audio output	inaudible 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9	audible 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9	NA
11.6	Exchanging data	difficult 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9	easy 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9	NA

Please write your comments about teleconferencing here:

PART 12: Software Installation

12.1	Speed of installation	slow 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9	fast 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9	NA
12.2	Customization	difficult 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9	easy 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9	NA
12.3	Informs you of its progress	never 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9	always 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9	NA
12.4	Gives a meaningful explanation when failures occur	never 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9	always 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9	NA

Please write your comments about software installation here:

APPENDIX F

TABLE OF EVIDENCE

Table 1
Factors Related To Mammography Use among Women Veterans and the Impact of Current Practice Structure

Purpose	Design, Key Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Key Findings	Author Conclusions	Limitations, Notes
To assess the use of screening reminders, recall, & outreach for cancer. (BS & CRS) (Fortuna et al., 2013).	Pragmatic randomized trial-staff blinded Off-site blinded statistician assigned 1,008 pts. into one of four intervention groups (BS, CRS, or both), stratified by screening required.	Rochester, New York, mainly low-income, disproportionately minority pt. pop., urban federal-designated (academic practice) underserved area. 50-74 yrs. old men/women for CRS (629) 40-74 yrs. old, women past due for BS (624)	Reminder, recall, & outreach (RRO) model 4 Groups (BS only) 1. Letter only (157) 2. Letter + Autodial (158) 3. Letter + Autodial + Prompt -in-reach (156) 4. Letter + Personal Call (PC) – Outreach (153)	Letter vs letter & PC 17.8% vs. 27.5% ; AOR 2.2, 95% CI 1.1-3.9) – PC more effective Letter vs. letter, autodial, & prompt (17.8% vs. 28.2% ; AOR 2.1, CI 1.1-3.7) Letter vs. letter & autodial – not more effective Group #4 more BS with call than those not reached (30.9% vs. 20.2%; $P = 0.05$)	Personalized outreach & directed in-reach (provider prompt) most effective to ↑ screening rates than a reminder letter alone	Setting is not generalizable; baseline screening rates were rather low. Possible pts. may have had an undocumented BS. Cost was not assessed.
BS evaluation of telephone advising & turnout in national BS program.	Prospective RCT IV: Telephone Counseling, Attendance in a	Greifswald Mammo - screening unit (1 of 4 units) in Mecklenburg-Vorpommern in	Telephone counseling, February to July 2008 Mammo use within 3 months after the	Screening attendance ↑-intervention grp. (Telephone & letter) vs. control	Barrier-specific counseling in addition to a reminder for non-responders ↑ BS	No demographic background collected, low reach of telephone

Purpose	Design, Key Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Key Findings	Author Conclusions	Limitations, Notes
(Hegenscheid et al., 2011).	national BS program DV: BS completion	Germany 5,477 women aged 50-69 yrs. old – non responders, Intervention group (2455), Control group (2952)	reminder. Reminder letter to control group, Reminder letter & telephone counseling – intervention group Satisfaction Survey: To ask counseled women about telephone counseling experience, & if it influenced decision to get BS, & socio-demographic data.	grp. (only letter) (29.7% vs. 26.1%, $p = .0035$) Drilled down only women with telephone numbers – (35.5% vs. 29.7%, $p = .0004$) Satisfaction Survey: 278/404 surveyed. 33% counseling influenced decision, 56% received BS, & 77% agreed counseling should be used for to encourage non-responders.	rates. To reach the subgroup pop. combination of telephone counseling & ↓ structural barriers (free transportation & cost) Telephone counseling was well accepted by participants & effective.	numbers, problem with making contacts before appts., no cost analysis
Women Veteran (WV) characteristics, needs, & preferences in VA system of care. (Mengeling, Sadler, Torner, & Booth, 2011)	Descriptive, Quantitative, Cross-sectional IV: Demographics, Military history, Perceptions & preferences DV: Use of VA Healthcare: All, Some or None	2005-2008 Two Midwestern VA's 1,002 woman 20-52 yrs old, 94% enlisted with a median of 4 years, 30% SA during military service, 50% SA outside of service.	Computer-assisted telephone interviews, using VisTa VA software (1,002), Health Survey Short Form-12 (SF-12); Post-traumatic Symptom Scale (PTSS) – 17 items; Composite International Diagnostic Interview (CIDI-SF) –	Preferences: WV prefer female provider ($p = .002$), Perceptions: WV agrees VA care is good, feel safe, & privacy. Rural WV ↓ need for separate waiting area just for women ($p < .01$), or want a	WV want gender specific care, “female chaperone” during exams, Care preferences similar irrespective of VA use but higher with WV users of VA care solely than non-VA users.	Limitations: Non-response bias - 29% never reached, self-reporting, & generalizability since selected population from Midwest, no question if WV knew that VA provides gender specific care.

Purpose	Design, Key Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Key Findings	Author Conclusions	Limitations, Notes
			depression scale; Lifetime Sexual Assault (LSA); WV preferences & perceptions interview – 5 point Likert scale	chaperone in room ($p < .05$), or treatment by male or female provider ($p < .01$)		
To document characteristics of WV challenges with access to care whether delayed and/or unmet. (Washington, Bean-Mayberry, Riopelle, & Yano, 2011)	Descriptive, Quantitative, Cross-sectional IV: Multiple IVs DV: Access to care	Stratified random sample based on VA use & nonuse, prior service. Exclusion criteria - currently serving, VA employee or institutionalization (3,611 consented)	2008 – 2009 National Survey of Women Veterans Telephone Survey Consumer Assessment of Health Plans Survey (CAHPS)	WV that experienced delay or went without healthcare in prior 12 months (18%), uninsured (54.6%), insured (14.3%) WV with deferred care or unmet needs related to those without – racial ethnic minorities, lacked consistent provider, uninsured, low, income, fair or poor health, disabled, mental health diagnosis.	Nearly 1 in 5 WV deferred healthcare or went with unmet needs in prior 12 months. Access barriers challenging - recognized VA's are in position to create programs to counterbalance SES & insurance-related barriers.	Limitations: Sampling problem with those without a telephone.
Identified barriers to access of care in the Veterans Health Administration (VHA) for WV. (Vogt et al., 2006)	Descriptive, Quantitative, Cross-sectional IV: Multiple IVs DV: Barriers to care	NRWV database – stratified random sampling – a subset of a larger sample (942 total - 543 current VHA users & 399 former users)	5 focus groups to probe for potential problems to accessing care. Barrier themes identified & items established to report	Availability of women- specific services - strongest predictor of VHA use by WV. Additional barriers: MD sensitivity,	WV perceived VHA care to be similar to other facilities. WV identified 2 areas for focus: 1) improving logistics (waiting time, continuity of care) & 2) women-	Limitation: Sampling bias of self-selection Notes: Older article – appropriate for benchmark data & awareness of factors

Purpose	Design, Key Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Key Findings	Author Conclusions	Limitations, Notes
			each of the themes for telephone survey. SF-36 Health Survey using a 5-point scale	logistics of care, facility/physical environment, insurance coverage, health status, & disability ratings.	specific services.	for potential recommendations.
What are deterrents & influences that affect why WV chose to use or not use Veteran Affairs (VA) Healthcare? (Washington, Yano, & Simon, 2006)	Descriptive, Quantitative, Cross-sectional IV: Multiple IVs DV: WV Use or nonuse of the VA Healthcare	WV users & WV non-users – Southern California & Southern Nevada (2,174) Randomly selected – stratified by ambulatory care (VA use, VA Nonuser), age group (< 50, 50 & older)	Telephone Survey (March – September 2004) VA utilization, attitudes toward care & socio-demographics CAHPS & SF-12	Reasons for use of VA care – Affordability (67.9%), availability WHC (58.8%), convenience (47.9%). Reason for nonuse– have personal insurance (71.0%), non-VA care more convenient (66.9%), not aware of available female services (48.5%), non-VA care perceived to be better (34.5%). Socio-demographic similarities of VA/non-VA users - age, race-ethnicity, period of service.	Multiple reasons for non-use of VA services – lack of knowledge about VA care, perceptions about excellence of care, untimeliness of care.	Limitations: Only people with telephones, Southern California & Southern Nevada Notes: Benchmark of where VA has been & provides statistics that would have included VA Long Beach - Part of Veterans Integrated Service Network 22 (VISN22) Targeted population, findings can support recommendations for focused practice change

Purpose	Design, Key Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Key Findings	Author Conclusions	Limitations, Notes
				VA users' \geq unemployed disabled, < \$20,000 annual income, uninsured, have service-connected disability, ($p < .0001$).		
Utilizing a conceptual framework to identify social & economic factors of WV in the United States that affects or influences the demand for mammo screenings. (Lairson, Chan, & Newmark, 2005)	Descriptive, Quantitative, Cross-sectional Design IV: Multiple IV's (28) specified as categorical DV: binary variable did get a mammo & did not (WV getting a mammo for diagnostic were excluded)	National Registry of Women Veterans (NRWV) – random sample – (3,415), 3 x 2 strata 2 cohorts - Fall 2000 & Summer 2001	Mail survey with telephone follow up Michael Grossman's model demand for health & medical care framework - understand utilization of preventative medical care	Significant: Insurance, income, apparent risk, smoking practice, & waiting & exam time Not Significant: Age categories, education levels, marital status, health conditions, race, & travel time	Grossman's framework fails to consider uncertainty. Age & poor health status – not directly related: education, insurance, income & perceived risk directly related to probability of use of screening BS.	Limitations: Limited data on BS & other preventative health behaviors for WV. Notes: Four key lessons to help remove barriers & decrease disparities in the conclusion section.
Is absence of screening, detection or follow-ups contributing factors in late-stage breast cancer? (Taplin et al., 2004)	Descriptive, Retrospective chart review Assigned women into 2 groups based on the stage of their breast cancer at diagnosis.	Cancer Research Network (7 health care plans) 1347 Case Subjects (metastatic and/or tumor \geq 3 cm & 1347 Control Subjects (early-stage)	Comparisons between the 2 groups – logistic regression for matched pairs. Models included age and year of diagnosis Cochran-Mantel-Haenszel statistic used to conduct a chi-	Not Significant: Hispanic origin, race, marital status, family history of breast cancer, median household income, or education Significant:	In order to reduce late-stage cancer, setting priorities for screening improvements can help to identify gaps in the screening process. Knowing the potential breakdown areas in	Limitations: Using chart review data imposes inherent limitations of observational research. Unknown characteristics of case subjects excluded from sample from 2 sites.

Purpose	Design, Key Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Key Findings	Author Conclusions	Limitations, Notes
			square test Unconditional logistic regression – association between absence of screening & variables of interest among case subjects	Screening Absence (all women) higher incidence of late-stage cancer (OR = 2.77, 95% CI = 1.84 to 2.56; $p < .001$) Case pts. 75 yrs. or older more likely in absence of screening group (OR = 2.77, 95% CI = 2.10 to 3.65), unmarried (OR = 1.78, 95% CI = 1.41 to 2.240, or no family history of breast cancer (OR = 1.84 95% CI = 1.45 to 2.34)	communication and follow-ups can provide a guide for establishing the priorities for improving the screening process.	Used data from 4 of the 7 sites – uncertainty of the overall estimated amount of women with invasive cancer in the target population Notes: Supports need to track and reach out to screen women who have not had a mammo in last 2 yrs.
What types of mammo outreach interventions are successful with the current population of WVs? (Dalessandri, Cooper, & Rucker, 1998)	Random Controlled Trial (based on even & odd endings of SSN) Randomly assigned into 2 Groups – 717 underserved WVs	VA Palo Alto Healthcare System (VAPAHCS) Group 1 (351) control – sent information on need for mammo, letter included identifying if due for mammo or if felt a lump. Group 2 (366) Intervention - sent above plus received	Demographic data questionnaire (age, branch of service, marital status, race, employment status) Over 6 month period – did or did not receive mammo	17 in Group 1 versus 100 in Group 2 received a mammo ($p < .01$) Demographics were similar	Having a nurse follow up call to schedule & answer questions resulted in 5-fold improvement over 6 months. Barriers to regular mammos (cost, lack of referral by a health care professional, lack of general education about breast cancer & mammo	Notes: May only be generalizable to other VA facilities. Older data, good study to be benchmark & compare current practices No assessment of education level or reference to literacy level of brochures –

Purpose	Design, Key Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Key Findings	Author Conclusions	Limitations, Notes
		a call from a breast care nurse – if no response within 45 days from mailer.				may have impacted results.
Explored possible predictors of WV in mammo use. (Hynes, Bastian, Rimer, Sloane, & Feussner, 1998)	Descriptive, Quantitative Design IV: Predictors DV: Women Veterans mammo use	Defense Manpower Data of U.S. DOD & national VA databases at the Austin (Texas) Automation Center. All living WV discharged 1971-1994 Two-phase sampling: Age ≥ 35 years old, served 18 months & discharged 1971-1994 (20,000 WV met criteria – 10% sample taken) Stratified random sample (n = 397) to complete pilot survey & tracking technique Attrition – final (n = 290)	Telephone survey – 2 purposes (pilot survey, pilot tracking techniques) 102-item survey & on 100 subjects Subset of 102-item survey & tracking techniques	Demographics - 44% - total VA users, 39% (114) 50-64 yrs., 12% (34) ≥ 65 yrs., 10% black, 40% spent 3-9.5 yrs. in service, 36% spent > 9.5 yrs. Weighted logistic regression model for predicting BS (BS use ever) - WV advised to have BS [OR 5.41, CI 4.64-6.32], (p = ≤ .001) WV 50-64 yrs. ↑ have BS than 35-49 yrs. [OR 4.65, CI 2.16-9.98], (p = ≤ .001) Black WV ↓ to have BS than nonblack [OR 0.65, CI 0.53-0.79], (p = ≤ .001) WV used VA in last 5 years ↑ BS [OR, 1.68, CI 1.34-	Future studies need to focus on provider patient communication, increasing provider's participation in WV discussions. First study to examine factors that affect BS use among WV.	Limitations: Pilot survey – possible overstated BS rates, inability to distinguish between screening & diagnostic mammo, small sample size Notes: Did not provide questions used in the survey – 102 questions are a lot of questions. Was it validated & reliable?

Purpose	Design, Key Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Key Findings	Author Conclusions	Limitations, Notes
				2.11], ($p = \leq .001$)		

Notes. AOR = Adjusted Odds Ratio, BRFSS = Behavioral Risk Factor Surveillance System, BS = Breast Screening, CRS = colorectal screening, CI = Confidence Interval, CAHPS = Consumer Assessment of Health Plans Survey, DOD = Department of Defense, DV = Dependent Variable, IV = Independent Variable, IRB = Institutional Review Board, mammo = mammography/mammogram, MST = Military Sexual Trauma, NRWV = National Registry of Women Veterans, n = number per group, OR = Odds Ratio, OEF/OIF/OND = Operation Enduring Freedom, Operation Iraqi Freedom, Operation New Dawn, PC = personal call, pop. = population, RCT = Randomized Control Trial, SA = Sexual assault, SSN = Social Security Number, SES = Socioeconomic status, UK = United Kingdom, U.S. = United States, VA = Veteran Affairs, VAPAHCS = Veteran Affairs Palo Alto Healthcare System, VHA = Veterans Health Administration, VISN22 = Veterans Integrated Service Network (22 is the region), WHC = Women’s Health Clinic, WV = women Veteran, yrs. = years old

Table 2

Integrated Review: International Women Population and Factors Affecting Breast Screening Compliance

Purpose	Design	Sample	Findings	Conclusions	Limitations, Notes
To explore factors that influence having breast cancer screenings. (Edgar, Glackin, Hughes, & Rogers, 2013)	Integrative Review Aim: To critically review factors which can influence women's decisions to get breast cancer screenings?	12 research papers Integrative review included U.S., UK, Australia, & Canada & Arab countries. Multiple types of research studies included: Primary research, theoretical, qualitative, quantitative, published from 2000, including explicit themes related to topic	4 BS influenced themes 1. Psychological, real-world issues, 2. Concerns related to ethnicity, 3. Impact of SES, & 4. Problems related to programs Mistaken perceptions & underestimation of individual risk related with low compliance. African American woman screening rates < Caucasian. Some health care professionals "... do not appreciate the value & impact of discussing mammo screenings & fail to make use of	Regardless of demographics, cognitive & psychological factors can influence screenings & can be used to educate & improve knowledge. Values & beliefs need to be considered. Literature should be delivered in primary language. Some providers fail to make use of opportunities. Cultural background influential in screening participation. Mammo rates significantly lower for women from ↓ SES backgrounds, ↓ level of education, with ↓ access screening	Women overestimate benefits, lack knowledge of risk associated with mammos. Women should be provided balanced information about risk & benefits of breast cancer screenings. Notes: While this review was completed in the UK, there are some commonalities between the U.S. & UK.

Purpose	Design	Sample	Findings	Conclusions	Limitations, Notes
			opportunities to raise awareness of breast cancer risk factors.” (p. 1025)	information & therefore do not recognize the benefits of early detection.	

Note. BS = breast screening, mammo = mammogram/mammography, SES = socioeconomic status, UK = United Kingdom, U.S. = United States

Table 3
Systematic Review: Value of Interventions to Improve Screenings for Breast Cancer

Purpose	Design	Sample	Findings	Conclusions	Limitations, Notes
Evaluates intervention to increase recommendations & deliver by healthcare providers (Baron et al., 2010)	Systematic Review	Studies between 1986 to November 2004 26 studies included Inclusion Criteria: a) Primary scientific publications, b) Reported using provider reminders, & c) Good quality of execution.	Effectiveness: BS ↑ median of 10% (IQI, 3.0%-19.0%) – no significance regarding method of prompt (electronic vs manual), distribution, content, format (client-specific vs generic), or provider experience. Applicability: BS ↑ in completed screening, recommendations, or ordered screenings. Economic Efficiency: BS cost effectiveness for tagging charts of women who received routine mammo, & for failed attendance in the past when they were due.	Robust evidence – provider prompt & recall systems provide positive results Applicable across wide variety of clinical settings, pt./provider population, plus irregularly or never screened patients. Intervention(s) to be utilized will rely on familiarity of local setting, culture, needs, repeat hx, & delivery choices.	Review does not provide specific guidance for which recommended intervention is most applicable for a population or setting.

Purpose	Design	Sample	Findings	Conclusions	Limitations, Notes
Evaluates effectiveness of interventions to ↑ BS, Cervical, & Colorectal screenings. (Sabatino et al., 2012)	Systematic Review update for the GCPS	9 interventions reviewed	<u>Increasing Community Demand for BS</u>	Local needs, barriers, populations, resources, evidence data – need consideration in choosing effective interventions.	No limitations listed by authors.
		45 studies included	Recommended: Sufficient evidence - (a) group education	Evaluation of interventions that worked – significant stage to improve increase screening.	Note: potential influences that need to be further studied – Communication (e.g. texting, internet, e-mail, social media & AIVR)
		Studies between January 2004 to October 2008	Recommended: Strong evidence - (a) individual education, (b) client prompt	Critical to disseminate findings of effective interventions to maximize utility	
		Inclusion Criteria:	Insufficient evidence – (a) client incentives, (b) mass media		
		a) Primary investigation of one or more interventions,			
		b) Conducted in high-income economy country,			
		c) Obtained one cancer screening,	<u>Increasing Community Access to Screening for BS</u>		
		d) Screening use prior to intervention execution, &	Recommended: Sufficient evidence – (a) reducing personal cost		
		e) Current group not exposed to intervention	Recommended: Strong evidence – (a) reducing structural barriers		
			<u>Increasing Provider Support of Screening for BS</u>		

Purpose	Design	Sample	Findings	Conclusions	Limitations, Notes
			<p>Recommended: Sufficient evidence – (a) provider assessment & feedback</p> <p>Insufficient evidence – (a) provider incentives</p>		

Note: appt. = appointment, AIVR = automated interactive voice response, BS = breast screening, GCPS = Guide to Community Preventive Services, hx = history, IQI = interquartile interval, mammo = mammogram/mammography, pt. = patient

Table 4
Table of Evidence for Qualitative Studies

Purpose	Conceptual /Theoretical Underpinnings, Design	Sample & Setting	Data Collection, Management & Analysis	Results; Theoretical Integration	Author Conclusions; Limitations; Notes
To explore WVs views & considerations about VA healthcare use. (Washington, Kleimann, Michelini, Kleimann, & Canning, 2007)	Ethnographic Qualitative, exploratory, & descriptive.	51 VA eligible WVs Met in professional focus group (grp) settings Recruited through facility contacts & mailed invitation letter. \$50 incentive for time	6 focus grps – stratified (VA use & age grp), 4 grps (used VA with in past 5 yrs.), 2 grps (never used VA or not used in last 5 yrs), 2 VA-user grps & 1 nonuser were with WVs having served before 1980, remainder grps with WVs severing since 1980. 1 1/2 to 2 hours audio & videotaped. Semi-structured interviews, written survey to collect demographic info. Transcript-based content analysis – grounded theory methodology- Glaser & Strauss, data analyzed by coding till themes/categories fully developed with constant comparison method by all 3 investigators, to enhance reliability 2 additional investigators used same process, representative quotes	Focus grps represented a range of ages & demographics, 47% VA users below federal poverty level, with no nonusers in this category, 62% VA users & 94% on nonusers had health insurance. 3 major themes developed as qualities WVs seek in their healthcare: (a) access, (b) gender appropriateness, & (c) quality. Same 3 themes appeared for decision-making about VA use with an additional theme of information needs. Barriers – lack of knowledge of services & eligibility – nonusers no aware of WV services Users/nonusers expressed a requirement for quality & gender sensitivity care. Users/nonusers views of VA quality differed. VA setting (male dominated) concerns was identified as a limitation of use.	Perceptions, experiences, environmental, & quality concerns are often related to WV healthcare needs which can contribute & influence their choice in deciding to use VA care. There is a knowledge gap about the VA eligibility & WV services. Study conducted in one geographic area is a limitation. This study informs the VA about WV perspective on VA healthcare & the results should be priority areas for improvement as identified by the WVs.

Purpose	Conceptual /Theoretical Underpinnings, Design	Sample & Setting	Data Collection, Management & Analysis	Results; Theoretical Integration	Author Conclusions; Limitations; Notes
			extracted supporting themes & tones communicated.		

Note: grp(s) = group(s), info. = information, VA = Veterans Affairs, WV = women veteran, yrs. = years

Table 5
Use of Databases to Improve Clinical Outcomes

Purpose	Design	Sample	Findings	Conclusions	Limitations, Notes
Improving quality and efficiency interventions for breast cancer screenings in a heterogeneous primary care network. (Lester, Ashburner, Grant, Chueh, Barry, & Atlas, 2009)	Performance Improvement - Mammography FastTrack (MFT) installation and implementation usage	Massachusetts General Primary Care Network (MGPCN) – over 150,000 patients (pt.), 180 primary care physicians (PCP) 3,054 eligible pts. 64 PCP managed pts. – 1,689, 6 Case Manager (CM) managed pts. – 1,365 – tested in 6 primary cares within network	After 6 months – 86% of PCPs & all CMs used a portion of MFT, PCPs intervened in 83% of overdue mammograms (letters sent and or deferred contact), 63% pts. successfully contacted.	Technology integration success is supported by accommodating the PCP, practice workflow in flexible environment, simple and convenient screenings, automated surveillance and pt. outreach methods.	Even with considerations of allowing as much local workflow flexibility – unable to meet every practices preference. No system in place to identify or send reminders for overdue mammograms System requires manual upload of at risk population, mammography due dates & updated link to provider.
Utilizing technology to improve workflow. (Corkery, 2007)	Performance Improvement	4 Inpatient Rehabilitation Care Management Team (IRCMT) members, admissions nurse (ARN), nursing administrator Questionnaires and meetings used to assess what was working and what was not.	Duplication (over 300 data items used more than once) in work processes found in existing paper system Timing trial – 3 to 3½ hours of redundancy	Identify strengths and weaknesses of process and integrate into planning. Consideration of end-users – satisfaction is a direct link to participation and bidirectional communication. Time-saving – partially achieved	Designing takes considerable time and effort Loss of real-time reports and statistics - Information Technology (IT) personnel required to export from both excel and the web-based database into the departments database Original design not

Purpose	Design	Sample	Findings	Conclusions	Limitations, Notes
					used – change in project – project champion transferred out of department
Evaluating a user satisfaction with a clinical database. (Hortman & Thompson, 2005)	Descriptive, Quantitative Evaluating a mock nurse practitioner (NP) outcomes database – developed to track clients clinical outcomes	Midwestern College of Nursing Convenience sample – 5 faculty NPs Questionnaire for User Interaction Satisfaction (QUIS) – Demographic data, 12 parts with 2 & 7 excluded.	Individual QUIS results ranged from 3.0 to 8.0. Overall user satisfaction moderately high.	There is no one size fits all. Designers can get too close or too comfortable with design and may not recognize existing problems. Formal evaluation and observation important part of the design process	QUIS – developed at the University of Maryland in 1980s – Cronbach alpha of 0.95, Likert scale 1 – 9 Small sample size

Note: ARN = Admissions Nurse, NA = Nursing Administrator, IT = Information Technology, IRCMT = Inpatient Rehabilitation Care Management Team, MFT = Mammography FastTrack, MGPCN = Massachusetts General Primary Care Network, NP = Nurse Practitioner, pt. = patient, PCP = Primary Care Physician
QUIS = Questionnaire for User Interaction Satisfaction.

